

Formation Constants of N(2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene)- β -alanine Complexes of Cobalt (II), Nickel(II), Copper(II), Zinc(II) and Uranyl (II)

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Potentiometric studies have been carried on metal complexes of Cobalt (II), Nickel (II), Copper (II), Zinc (II) and Uranyl (II) with N(2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene)- β -alanine ($H_2N\beta A$). The dissociation constants ($pK_1 = 5.50$ and $pK_2 = 9.60$) of $H_2N\beta A$ and the formation constants of its metal complexes (1.1) have been determined by Bjerrum's method at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The order of stability is found to be $UO_2 > Cu > Ni > Co > Zn$, which is in accordance with Irving and Williams rule.

A survey of the literature shows no reference of the formation of $H_2N\beta A$ complexes with Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and UO_2^{2+} . It is, therefore, of interest to investigate the dissociation constants of $H_2N\beta A$ and formation constants of its metal complexes.

EXPERIMENTAL

All chemicals used were of either B.D.H. 'AnalaR' or Riedle Germany. The ligand was synthesised¹ and its standard solution was prepared in 60-40 (v/v) water-dioxan mixture. The metal nitrate solutions were prepared in double-distilled water.

pH of the solutions was measured by using DORAN pH-meter.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Bjerrum's pH-titration technique² was adopted for obtaining the stepwise stability constants of the complexes of Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and UO_2^{2+} with $H_2N\beta A$. A bulk of electrolyte of μ 0.1 M sodium perchlorate was adopted to maintain the constant ionic strength and reaction solutions were all thermostated at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$.

The formation curve (Fig. 1) of the ligand extends up to $\bar{n}_A = 2.0$, which indicates that two protons respectively from carboxylic and phenolic groups are dissociated. The dissociation constants (pK_1 and pK_2) obtained from this curve by an adoption of Bjerrum's method² and Algebraic method³ are 5.50, 9.60 and 5.48, 9.52 respectively.

In calculating the values of \bar{n} and A^- , the concentrations were corrected for changes in volume produced by the addition of alkali during titration. In this way a series of values of \bar{n} and A^- , corresponding to different values of pH were obtained in each case. Formation curves were obtained by plotting \bar{n} against $\log A^-$ as given in Fig. 2.

The values for $\log K_1$ for Cobalt, Nickel, Copper, Zinc and Uranyl complexes with $H_2N\beta A$ were directly read from their formation curves. These have been given in Table I.

TABLE I

Stability of Metal Complexes of N(2-hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene)-β-alanine

$\mu = 0.1 M NaClO_4$

Temp. = $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$

Metal	At No.	2nd I.P.	Electro-negativity	$\log K_1$
Co	27	17.30	1.70	5.60
Ni	28	18.20	1.75	6.20
Cu	29	20.34	1.75	8.85
Zn	30	17.89	1.66	4.95
UO ₂	—	—	—	9.30

Table-1 indicates that $\log K_1$ values of these complexes follow the order Uranyl > Copper > Nickel > Cobalt > Zinc which is in accordance with Irving-Williams order⁴.

A parallelism between $\log K$ and 2nd Ionisation potential (I.P.) (Fig. 3) is also observed in the present case⁵ as has already been suggested by Irving and Williams. Except for Zinc, this potential measures the energy required for the removal of a d -electron suggesting the involvement of d -orbitals in the complex formation.

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